

bicarbonate solution (5%) and water and dried over Na_2SO_4 (anhydrous). Removal of the solvent yielded the tetrazole (4) which was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5), (1.625 g), m.p. 186° (Found: C, 64.1; H, 8.9; N, 11.1. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_4\text{Br}$ requires: C, 64.14; H, 8.97, N, 11.08%); positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 520 (C=N), 1 465 and 1 380 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ 5.5 (1H, s, C7 α -H), 4.7 (1H, dd, J_{aa} 10, J_{ab} 7 Hz, C5 α -H), 1.23 (C10- CH_3), 0.57 (C13- CH_3), 0.91, 0.8 and 0.67 (other angular methyl protons).

Under similar reaction conditions (using equal amounts of the reactants), the bromo ketones 2 and 3 afforded the tetrazoles 5 and 6, respectively. The tetrazole 5 was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5), (1.728 g), m.p. 191° (Found: C, 60.1; H, 8.1; N, 10.3. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{BrCl}$ requires: C, 60.05; H, 8.12; N, 10.37%); positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 525 (C=N), 1 465, 1 380 (N=N) and 735 cm^{-1} (CCl); δ 5.5 (1H, C7 α -H), 4.71 (1H, dd, J_{aa} 9, J_{ab} 7 Hz, C5 α -H), 3.87 (1H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 22 Hz, C3 α -H), 1.18 (C10- CH_3), 0.55 (C13- CH_3), 0.9, 0.8 and 0.65 (remaining methyl protons). The tetrazole 6 was recrystallised from chloroform-methanol (1 : 5) (1.637 g), m.p. 204° (Found: C, 61.7; H, 8.4; N, 2.8. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Br}$ requires: C, 61.8; H, 8.40; N, 2.84%); positive Beilstein test; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 735 (CH_3COO), 1 235, 1 040 (C-O), 1 520 (C=N), 1 465 and 1 370 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ 5.53 (1H, C7 α -H), 4.67-4.9 (2H, m, $W_{1/2}$ 24 Hz, C3 α -H, C5 α -H), 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3COO), 1.2 (C10- CH_3), 0.58 (C13- CH_3), 0.9, 0.81 and 0.68 (other methyl protons).

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Synthesis and Pharmacological Activity of 1-Benzamide-2-phenyl-4- benzylideneimidazoline-5-one

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THE benzylidene imidazolinones are biologically active¹. Interaction of amine with 2-aryl-4-arylidene-2-oxazolin-5-one, under the influence of acetic acid and sodium acetate, yields the corresponding imidazolin-5-ones². Benzocaine and its derivatives are reported as antitubercular³ and bacteriocidal⁴.

Thiosemicarbazone and related compounds of vanillin have been screened against bacteria and fungi substitution with NO_2 or Br seemed to enhance the activity⁵. The structure modification with pharmacologically active grouping have shown excellent results in pharmacology. The title compounds were prepared according to Scheme 1.

R = Different aromatic moieties.

Scheme 1